

Modeling Disinformation Spread in Social Networks: Phase Transitions and Mean-Field Analysis

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Abstract—The pervasive spread of disinformation across social media platforms has become a significant global challenge, disrupting democratic processes, undermining public trust and fueling societal polarization. Existing approaches often neglect the dynamic and structural mechanisms that drive the spread and adoption of false narratives. This paper leverages the well-established principles and methodologies of Statistical Mechanics and introduces a dynamic Mean-Field framework to model the evolution of disinformation within social networks. The framework introduces innovative elements, including heterogeneous coupling strengths to capture diverse social influences among network users, memory effects to account for cognitive inertia or belief re-evaluation and a three-state Potts model to represent polarization and neutrality in opinion dynamics. It employs the concept of effective fields to integrate external disinformation campaigns, facilitating a detailed analysis of critical thresholds and phase transitions. Monte Carlo simulations are performed to further illustrate the transient and equilibrium dynamics of belief adoption and rejection. Our findings provide actionable insights for the disinformation spread and offer a theoretical foundation for designing targeted interventions to mitigate its harmful effects on societies.

Index Terms—Disinformation Spread, Social Media Networks, Statistical Mechanics, Mean-Field Theory, Stochastic Modeling, Polarization, Susceptibility, Network Dynamics, Influence Propagation

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid proliferation of disinformation has emerged as a critical threat to global stability and democratic processes. The digital landscape has facilitated the rapid dissemination of disinformation, with social media platforms serving as conduits for false narratives. Due to its widespread societal impact, the United Nations have defined disinformation as false information disseminated with the intent to deceive and cause serious harm¹. This includes content spread by both state and non-state actors, affecting a broad range of human rights and undermining responses to

public policies or amplifying tensions during emergencies or armed conflicts. The World Economic Forum's Global Risks Report 2024² identified disinformation as the most significant short-term risk worldwide, highlighting the profound impact of false information on societies.

In late 2024, Meta dismantled approximately 20 covert influence operations worldwide, highlighting the persistent efforts of state and non-state actors to manipulate public opinion³. Interestingly enough, the same organization announced in January 2025 the termination of its third-party fact-checking program in the United States, transitioning to a Community Notes model inspired by X (formerly Twitter)⁴. While this move intended to reduce policy enforcement errors and enhance user autonomy, it raised several concerns about its ability to combat complex disinformation campaigns effectively, as the reliance on crowd-sourced moderation could amplify biases or overlook nuanced forms of manipulation, while also potentially reduce accountability in handling high-impact content. Given the scale and sophistication of modern disinformation campaigns, there is an urgent need for comprehensive frameworks to deeper understand and mitigate their spread.

Traditional approaches, such as fact-checking and crowd-sourced moderation, while extremely valuable, often fall short in addressing the dynamic and multifaceted nature of disinformation. In addition to detecting false information, effective frameworks must also analyse the underlying mechanisms of its propagation including the role of key influential users, targeted narratives and user susceptibility. Such frameworks can offer practical guidance on key intervention points and shape effective strategies to mitigate its harmful effects on democratic systems, public trust, social cohesion and global stability. Without these approaches, any effort to contain disinformation spread

2. Global Risks Report 2024, World Economic Forum, 10 January, 2024

3. Meta says it has taken down about 20 covert influence operations in 2024, The Guardian, 3 December, 2024

4. Meta is getting rid of fact checkers. Zuckerberg acknowledged more harmful content will appear on the platforms now, CNN, 7 January, 2025

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1. United Nations, Information Integrity on Digital Platforms, June 2023.

will probably remain reactive rather than proactive, which would leave societies vulnerable to the disruptive impacts.

This paper presents a dynamic approach based on the Mean-Field theory for modeling the spread of disinformation and its evolution. It introduces several innovative aspects that advance the deeper understanding of belief dynamics in complex social networks. The proposed framework captures the time-dependent evolution of beliefs, offering insights into both transient dynamics and equilibrium states. Memory effects are also incorporated to reflect cognitive inertia, allowing the representation of how users reinforce or reconsider their past beliefs and aligning it with real-world behaviours where prior states influence decision-making.

Our approach incorporates heterogeneous coupling strengths that reflect the heterogeneity in social influence across users, acknowledging that certain users, such as influencers or media sources, wield considerably greater persuasive power than others. Polarization and neutrality are also captured based on the three-state Potts model, reflecting the spectrum of opinions seen in real-world scenarios, where users may fully adopt, reject or remain undecided about disinformation propaganda. The framework builds upon well-established methods from statistical mechanics in order to systematically analyze the spread of disinformation and identify critical thresholds and phase transitions and provide insights about the conditions under which disinformation spreads uncontrollably within the network.

In statistical mechanics, phase transitions describe abrupt changes in system behavior when certain parameters cross a critical threshold lead to a qualitative shift in the macroscopic state, such as the transition from liquid to gas in thermodynamic systems. Establishing a connection between magnetization in spin systems and belief alignment in social networks allows this framework to identify the conditions under which a small perturbation, such as an increase in external influence through a disinformation propaganda or an amplification of social reinforcement, triggers a rapid and widespread adoption of false narratives.

Additionally, the framework applies mean-field approximations to capture macroscopic trends in the system without requiring computationally expensive agent-based modeling. This approach enables an analytical estimation of the steady-state belief distributions and helps quantify the impact of different network structures, memory effects, and external fields on disinformation persistence. In particular, the model allows for the identification of conditions where disinformation becomes self-sustaining, meaning that even in the absence of external reinforcement, the system remains locked into a state of widespread belief in falsehoods. In addition, our approach enables the extensive analysis of targeted interventions along with their impact on belief dynamics through the integration of external fields that model disinformation campaigns or countermeasures.

Our framework excels at handling both stochasticity and heterogeneity which are two fundamental characteristics of real-world social networks. Unlike purely deterministic models, our approach enables the exploration of nonlinear dynamics, such as the interplay between external influence, social reinforcement and individual resistance to belief change. Additionally, our method provides a computation-

ally efficient alternative to large-scale simulations, rendering it more suitable for the analysis of realistic network structures. It enables the prediction of tipping points where small changes in external influence can result in abrupt shifts in public opinion. Most importantly, it provides actionable insights for policy interventions, assisting in the identification of the most effective strategies for counteracting disinformation prior to its widespread adoption.

Statistical mechanics provides a robust framework for modelling complex systems that comprise several interacting elements, making it particularly well-suited for studying the spread of disinformation in social networks. Techniques such as mean-field approximations [1], ensemble theory [2], Ising model [3] and Renormalization Group [4] enable statistical mechanics to identify macroscopic patterns that emerge from microscopic particle interactions. One of the key advantages of this field, is the ability to describe collective behavior through probabilistic models, facilitating the study of emergent phenomena in large, interacting systems without the need to track individual components in detail. Statistical mechanics connects small-scale interactions to large-scale phenomena, helping researchers analyze how local influences scale up to global patterns. Its methods are computationally efficient, improving the examination of large-scale networks while preserving key characteristics like stability conditions and critical thresholds. It is worth mentioning that statistical mechanics has been widely applied in domains such as information theory [5], computer networks [6], wireless communication networks [7], finance [8] and economics [9], politics [10], biology [11], just to name a few.

In summary the contributions of this work are the following:

- introduction of a dynamic Mean-Field framework to model disinformation spread, offering a novel approach that leverages statistical mechanics to capture belief evolution in social networks
- integration of memory effects to account for cognitive inertia, targeting a more realistic representation of how users retain and update their beliefs over time
- incorporation of heterogeneous coupling strengths, reflecting real-world variations in social influence since some users (e.g., influencers) have a disproportionate impact on opinion formation
- employment of a three-state Potts model, extending beyond binary belief systems and thus allowing for the coexistence of belief adoption, rejection and neutrality
- identification of critical thresholds and phase transitions, providing insights into when small perturbations can trigger large-scale belief shifts and thus creating suitable intervention strategies
- provision of a scalable and computationally efficient alternative for studying large-scale social networks without requiring extensive computational resources.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature on disinformation modeling, statistical mechanics approaches and social network analysis. Section 3 presents the proposed Mean-Field framework,

detailing the mathematical formulation. Section 4 describes the simulation setup, outlining the network structures, parameter choices and computational methodology along with discussion on the experimental results. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the key findings, highlights the novelties of the proposed approach and outlines directions for future research.

2 RELATED WORK

Researchers from various fields, including computer science, political science, information science, sociology [12] and linguistics [13], have extensively explored the identification and mitigation of fake news. Despite these efforts, effectively detecting and preventing the spread of fake news in real-world scenarios remains a significant challenge [14].

Numerous techniques have been introduced in the literature to analyze the spread of disinformation, leveraging insights from various fields. Several of them focus on content-level analysis [15]. These frameworks usually assume that linguistic patterns, claim structures and psychological cues embedded in text can serve as reliable predictors for detecting false information. However, they often omit considerations of how these narratives propagate within the social networks and how individual and collective belief dynamics evolve over time. The authors in [16] emphasized detecting fake news early using content-based features (e.g., linguistic and psychological attributes) without propagation data, aiming to intervene before disinformation spreads. The proposed theory-driven model examines in detail the micro-level content attributes, focusing on the nature and intent behind disinformation. Similarly, the authors in [17] presented a robust framework for detecting fact-checkable claims within textual data, creating an effective claim detection system that employed universal sentence representations. Nevertheless, these works focused exclusively on content-level detection, leaving unexplored the network-level dynamics and the social interactions that drive the propagation and adoption of disinformation.

In addition, network-based approaches [18] have been widely employed to model the structural and dynamic aspects of disinformation spread, leveraging graph theory to identify key influential nodes [19], predict propagation patterns [20] and assess the resilience of the social network to interventions. Epidemiological models, such as SIR (Susceptible-Infected-Recovered) and its variants [20], have been widely adapted to study the spread of disinformation in social networks. These models treat disinformation propagation analogously to disease transmission, with users transitioning between states like being susceptible, exposed to disinformation, actively sharing it, or recovering (e.g., rejecting the false information). Variants of these models introduce additional compartments, such as skeptics or fact-checkers, to capture subtle dynamics [21]. While these models provide a simple and intuitive framework, they face several drawbacks. First, they often assume homogeneous mixing, neglecting the complex heterogeneity of real-world social networks, where interactions vary in strength and structure. Moreover, epidemiological models frequently fail to consider key psychological and cognitive elements. For example, they often neglect how factors like confirmation

bias or the emotional pull of misleading information can make individuals more vulnerable.

Graph theory has been extensively used to analyze the structural aspects of disinformation spread within various forms of social networks. Centrality measures such as degree, betweenness and closeness have been widely used to identify key influential actors that amplify false narratives [22]. Community detection algorithms [23] have also been employed to identify clusters or echo chambers where disinformation can propagate more rapidly. At the same time, examining the network's structure can reveal patterns in how such information spreads through social connections. Despite its key advantages, graph theory presents significant limitations. It often relies on a static view of networks, which fails to capture the temporal and dynamic nature of real-world social interactions. Additionally, while structural metrics like centrality can identify key influential nodes, they often fail to neglect individual behavioral factors, such as how susceptible or resistant a user might be to disinformation. Graph-based approaches [24] also struggle to incorporate the role of external influences, such as orchestrated disinformation campaigns, and usually do not integrate linguistic or psychological factors, which ultimately limits their capacity to fully explain the complexities of how disinformation spreads.

The importance of analysing the dynamics and the underlying mechanisms that drive the dissemination of fake news across social media platforms has been emphasized in several studies [25], [26], especially since disinformation campaigns may lead to real-world online and physical crimes [27], [28]. These campaigns can inflame societal polarization, erode trust in public institutions and influence national elections. Moreover, the growing complexity of disinformation techniques, including the use of artificial intelligence, constitutes the need for advanced frameworks capable of modeling both the structural and temporal aspects of disinformation propagation, imperative. Addressing all these challenges requires an interdisciplinary approach that combines insights from network theory, behavioral science and computational analysis in order to predict, analyze and mitigate the spread of harmful narratives.

Our approach extends beyond existing studies by introducing a statistical mechanics framework that captures the structural and temporal evolution of disinformation while also identifies critical thresholds and phase transitions that govern its spread. While previous works have focused on network analysis, and computational detection techniques, they often lack a unified mathematical framework to quantify how local interactions scale into global belief dynamics. The increasing complexity of disinformation tactics, including AI-generated content and coordinated influence operations, demands a probabilistic approach capable of modelling stochasticity, non-linearity and emergent behavior in large-scale, complex social systems. Our proposed framework explores the tipping points where disinformation propaganda either collapses or becomes self-sustaining. This allows us to progress from descriptive analyses to formulating prediction insights regarding the evolution of belief alignment under varying network settings. The integration of these elements offers a computationally efficient and scalable alternative to agent-based simulations,

enabling the evaluation of counter-disinformation strategies and the assessment of network resilience against harmful narratives.

The fundamental principles of statistical mechanics provide a powerful framework for understanding the spread of disinformation by drawing parallels between belief dynamics in social networks and physical systems exhibiting collective behavior. Table 1 establishes this connection by translating key statistical mechanics concepts into their counterparts in disinformation modeling. This mapping allows non-experts to interpret how interactions between individuals, memory effects and external influences shape the global alignment of beliefs, offering a structured approach to analyzing the mechanisms driving the propagation of false narratives.

3 THE MEAN-FIELD APPROACH

Mean-Field theory [29] is a mathematical framework from statistical mechanics which is used to simplify the analysis of complex systems with many interacting components. Instead of modeling each individual interaction, the Mean-Field theory approximates the influence on a given element as the average effect (or “mean field”) of all others which reduces the complexity of the system while retaining essential macroscopic behaviors. The Mean Field method has been effectively applied in various fields [30] targeting optimization of resource allocation in ultra dense 5G and 6G networks [31], deeper understanding and analysis of the underlying mechanisms of multilayer neural networks [32], [33], optimization of emergency evacuation routes [34], [35], road traffic networks with autonomous vehicles [36] and demonstrating the versatility of the method in addressing complex technological challenges that involve large-scale interactions. In the context of disinformation spread, it approximates the dynamics of opinion or belief adoption in a social network by replacing detailed interactions with an average field.

We model our social network as a graph $G = (V, E)$ where nodes (V) represent the users and the edges (E) represent social connections or interactions, following a similar approach to [37]. We assume that each node i has a state $s_i \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$, where $+1$ indicates belief in disinformation, 0 neutral or undecided and -1 rejection. The state of node i is influenced by (a) the heterogeneous, non symmetric social coupling strengths, J_{ij} , between node i and its neighbors j , which represent the varying influence strengths across the network, (b) an external influence field, h_i , modeling targeted disinformation campaigns or counter-efforts and (c) the memory effects, μ , capturing the impact of a node’s past state $s_i(t-1)$ on its current state $s_i(t)$.

The effective field acting on node i is given by

$$h_i^{\text{eff}}(t) = \sum_j J_{ij} s_j(t) + h_i + \mu s_i(t-1), \quad (1)$$

where J_{ij} is the coupling strength between nodes i and j , h_i is the external field, which can vary across nodes and μ is the memory coefficient, with $\mu > 0$ reinforcing past beliefs and $\mu = 0$ in case past opinions are completely disregarded. The effective field quantifies the combined influence on an individual’s belief state at a given time t . It is the core

concept in the study of disinformation spread because it encapsulates the key drivers of opinion dynamics, i.e., the influence from social interactions, external disinformation campaigns and the user’s memory. The social interaction term [38] reflects how strongly the beliefs of neighbors j affect user i , with heterogeneous coupling strengths J_{ij} capturing variations in interpersonal influence (e.g., closer friends have a greater influence compared to more distant acquaintances). The external field h_i models targeted campaigns, such as disinformation propagated by bots or biased media sources, which can amplify specific narratives to influence beliefs. Finally, the memory term $\mu s_i(t-1)$ reflects an individual’s inherent inertia [39], where $\mu > 0$ reinforces past beliefs and $\mu = 0$ encourages re-evaluation.

In the context of disinformation, $h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)$ provides a concrete measure of the forces that shape an individual’s decision to adopt, reject or remain neutral toward a narrative. For instance, a strong positive $h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)$ indicates that the network user is exposed to significant social or external pressures to believe the disinformation. This could occur due to repeated exposure to false claims through trusted peers or well-orchestrated campaigns. Conversely, a negative $h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)$ might reflect counter-disinformation efforts, such as fact-checking or interventions by credible sources, which influence users to reject false narratives. The inclusion of memory further enriches the model, acknowledging that past beliefs often create cognitive inertia, making individuals less susceptible to external pressures [40]. This dynamic interaction of social, external and internal factors constitutes the effective field as a critical framework for understanding how disinformation spreads and stabilizes within a population.

The probability of node i transitioning to state $s_i(t+1) \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$ is

$$\mathbb{P}\left(s_i(t+1) \mid h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)\right) = \frac{\exp(\beta \mathcal{F}(s_i(t+1), h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)))}{\sum_{s'_i \in \{-1, 0, +1\}} \exp(\beta \mathcal{F}(s'_i, h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)))}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(s_i(t+1), h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)) = f(s_i(t+1)) g(h_i^{\text{eff}}(t))$ is the energy-like function for state s_i and β is the inverse temperature, controlling the randomness of state transitions. In our case, we consider $\mathcal{F}(s_i(t+1), h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)) = s_i(t+1) h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)$ derived from the classical energy formulation in spin systems, particularly from the Ising model, where interactions and external fields contribute to the system’s Hamiltonian in a linear fashion. In other words, we assume that a user’s updated belief $s_i(t+1)$ is directly proportional to the effective field acting upon them, not only for ensuring analytical tractability in a mean-field setting but also for mapping real-world dynamics where external campaigns, peer interactions and memory effects all shape belief evolution.

This probability reflects the likelihood of adopting, rejecting, or remaining neutral toward a narrative, based on the combined influences acting on the user. It is determined by the Boltzmann distribution, which integrates the effective field and the control parameter β . A high value of β corresponds to deterministic behavior, where users align more predictably with the dominant influences, while a low β value allows greater randomness in decision-making.

TABLE 1: Mapping of Statistical Mechanics Concepts to Disinformation Spread Analysis

Statistical Mechanics Concept	Disinformation Spread Analysis Counterpart
Spin State (s_i)	Belief state of an individual (+1: belief, -1: rejection, 0: neutral)
Lattice or Graph	Social network where nodes represent individuals and edges represent interactions
Coupling Strength (J_{ij})	Influence between individuals, accounting for heterogeneous social ties
External Field (h)	External influence, such as targeted disinformation campaigns or fact-checking efforts
Energy (\mathcal{F})	System-wide disinformation energy, quantifying the total influence and belief alignment
Inverse Temperature (β)	Randomness in belief adoption, with lower β indicating higher susceptibility to noise
Magnetization (m)	Global alignment of beliefs, representing the overall tendency to adopt or reject disinformation
Memory Term (μs_i)	Cognitive inertia, capturing the effect of past beliefs on current decisions
Phase Transition	Critical threshold of belief dynamics in social networks where disinformation spreads uncontrollably or stabilizes

The energy function $\mathcal{F}(s_i(t+1), h_i^{\text{eff}}(t))$ models how the local environment (neighboring influences, external field and memory effects) drives the state transitions of s_i . It serves as the “cost function” that dictates the probabilistic evolution of the system, balancing the tendency to minimize energy with thermal fluctuations controlled by β . In simple words, when $h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)$ is strongly positive, the probability of transitioning to +1 (adopting the disinformation) increases, while the probability of transitioning to -1 (rejecting the narrative) decreases. Neutrality ($s_i(t+1)=0$) may remain a viable option if the effective field is weak or conflicting.

The magnetization $m(t)$, representing the global belief dynamics, evolves as

$$m(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N s_i(t) \quad (3)$$

where $s_i(t)$ is the state of node i at time t . It captures the extent to which an individual’s belief fluctuates between adopting (+1), rejecting (-1), or remaining neutral (0). At the user’s level, $m_i(t)$ reflects the balance of competing influences: the social interactions with connected peers, external fields promoting or countering disinformation and the memory of past beliefs. When $m_i(t) > 0$, the individual is more inclined to adopt the disinformation, while $m_i(t) < 0$ indicates rejection. A value of $m_i(t) \approx 0$ reflects neutrality or indecision, often observed when the individual is exposed to equally opposing pressures. Aggregating $m_i(t)$ across all nodes in the network results in the global magnetization $m(t)$ which serves as a macroscopic measure of belief dynamics.

The change in magnetization over time depends on the collective dynamics

$$m(t+1) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{E}[s_i(t+1)] \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[s_i(t+1)]$ is the expected belief state of node i at $t+1$,

$$\mathbb{E}[s_i(t+1)] = \sum_{s_i \in \{-1, 0, +1\}} s_i \mathbb{P}(s_i(t+1) | h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)) \quad (5)$$

This expected value provides a probabilistic prediction of node i ’s next state based on the current effective field $h_i^{\text{eff}}(t)$. If the probability is heavily skewed toward a particular state (e.g., $\mathbb{P}(+1) \approx 1$), $\mathbb{E}[s_i(t+1)]$ approaches that state, reflecting

strong certainty about the node’s behaviour. Conversely, if probabilities are distributed more evenly across states, $\mathbb{E}[s_i(t+1)]$ will gravitate toward neutral values, indicating higher uncertainty. In Equation (5), we also perform summation over $s_i = 0$ which does not directly influence the expected magnetization but affects the normalization of probabilities. The presence of $s_i = 0$ effectively redistributes the probability mass across all possible belief states, influencing the likelihood of transitioning between $s_i = \pm 1$. This consideration is particularly relevant in social networks where a significant fraction of individuals may remain neutral or disengaged, neither fully adopting nor rejecting a given disinformation narrative.

The self-consistency equation for magnetization [41] evolves as:

$$m(t+1) = \tanh \left(\beta \left(\sum_j J_{ij} m_j(t) + h_i + \mu m(t) \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

which governs the evolution of the global belief dynamics over time, allowing the tracking of how beliefs spread over time. It establishes a feedback loop between the individual states of nodes and the aggregate behavior of the system, capturing how local interactions and external forces propagate through the network. This equation does not only predict the transient evolution of magnetization $m(t)$ but also provides insights into equilibrium states and critical transitions, such as the conditions under which disinformation becomes dominant or counter-narratives gain traction.

It is worth highlighting that in many models of social dynamics, the external field h_i represents a constant external influence acting on node i . This can be the persistent effect of a disinformation campaign targeting node i or a fixed bias or predisposition (e.g., political leaning, media exposure, etc.) that does not change significantly over time. In addition, many real-world scenarios, such as long-running disinformation campaigns, can be approximated with a constant external field. Thus, we assume a uniform external field h across all nodes, representing a global influence that affects the entire population in a homogeneous manner. This assumption allows us to focus on the collective behavior of belief dynamics rather than node-specific variations. While a node-dependent h_i could capture personalized susceptibility to external influence, our framework prioritizes a macroscopic understanding of disinformation propagation,

leaving heterogeneous external influences as a potential extension for future work.

The self-consistency equation for magnetization provides a compact theoretical framework for understanding the equilibrium behavior of belief dynamics. However, its inherent complexity stemming from the non-linear relationships between the magnetization m , external fields h , coupling strengths J_{ij} and memory effects μ , makes it analytically intractable. Thus, there is not an analytical solution which can address the full spectrum of dynamics in such systems.

3.1 Monte Carlo Simulations

The lack of analytical solutions reinforces the importance of a simulation-based approach for analysing how disinformation spreads through social networks. Monte Carlo methods [42] allows the exploration of the complex dynamics of disinformation propaganda, capturing both transient and steady-state behaviors in belief systems while addressing the inherent stochasticity and temporal dynamics of real-world scenarios. Furthermore, Monte Carlo simulations can naturally adapt to diverse network structures where analytical methods often fail due to the lack of symmetry and uniformity. The simulation of the microscopic interactions among the users of the social network enables the exploration of emergent macroscopic behaviors such as phase transitions and critical thresholds. More specifically, the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm [43], a widely used approach in Monte Carlo simulations, offers an efficient way to model the probabilistic evolution of individual states under the influence of social interactions and external fields. The algorithm, outlined in Algorithm 1, emulates real-world decision-making processes by flipping the state of randomly selected nodes in response to energy changes and thermal noise, thus incorporating both social influence and randomness in opinion dynamics. This approach facilitates the detailed modeling of the dynamics governing belief adoption and rejection, assess the system's sensitivity to external influences and delineates the conditions under which disinformation proliferates or is mitigates.

Following the arguments above, we model the social network $G = (V, E)$ and its underlying dynamics as an undirected graph where nodes represent the users and edges represent their interactions. Each node i has a state $s_i(t) \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$ as indicated above. The system's energy is generalized using an effective field-based Hamiltonian:

$$\mathcal{H}(t) = - \sum_{\langle i, j \rangle} J_{ij} s_i(t) s_j(t) - \sum_i h_i s_i(t) - \sum_i \mu s_i(t) s_i(t-1), \quad (7)$$

The summation $\langle i, j \rangle$ runs over all neighboring nodes i and j , encapsulating the structure of the network into the interactions. The term $s_i(t-1)$ represents the state of node i in the previous time step, introducing memory effects into the dynamics. The Monte Carlo simulation employs the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm for the probabilistic update of the node states $s_i(t)$. At each time step, the algorithm calculates the transition probability to a new state $s_i(t+1)$ based on the effective field defined in Eq. (5). It's overall complexity ranges from $\mathcal{O}(n_{\text{sweeps}} \cdot N)$ for sparse networks, e.g., Scale-Free and Small-World graphs to $\mathcal{O}(n_{\text{sweeps}} \cdot N^2)$

Algorithm 1: Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm for Disinformation Dynamics

Data: Graph topology (adjacency matrix A), heterogeneous coupling strengths J_{ij} , external field h_i , memory coefficient μ , inverse temperature β , number of sweeps n_{sweeps} .

Result: Magnetization $m(t)$ over time, representing the global belief alignment after the system reaches equilibrium.

Initialize: Randomly assign each node

$$s_i(0) \in \{-1, 0, +1\};$$

for $t = 1$ **to** n_{sweeps} **do**

At each time step, the system evolves by sequentially updating the states of nodes in the network;

for $n = 1$ **to** N **do**

Randomly select a node i from the network, representing a user whose belief state will be updated;

Compute the effective field acting on node i :

$$h_i^{\text{eff}}(t) = \sum_j J_{ij} s_j(t) + h_i + \mu s_i(t-1)$$

Compute the transition probabilities for each state based on the effective field:

$$\mathbb{P}[s_i(t+1) = s'] = \frac{\exp(\beta s' h_i^{\text{eff}}(t))}{\sum_{\tilde{s} \in \{-1, 0, +1\}} \exp(\beta \tilde{s} h_i^{\text{eff}}(t))}$$

Randomly sample a new state

$s_i(t+1) \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$ for node i based on $\mathbb{P}[s_i(t+1)];$

end

Compute the magnetization for the current time step:

$$m(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N s_i(t)$$

end

return $m(t)$ over all time steps to analyze belief dynamics and steady-state behavior;

for for dense networks such as fully connected graphs [44]. In realistic social networks, each user interacts only with a limited number of neighbours, thus the complexity is closer to $\mathcal{O}(n_{\text{sweeps}} \cdot N)$. This approach based on the Monte Carlo simulations, facilitates the computation of the system's macroscopic properties, such as the time-dependent magnetization $m(t)$, which quantifies the global alignment of beliefs across the network. Moreover, it captures the transient dynamics and equilibrium states, providing insights into the mechanisms that drive the spread and stabilization of fake news and disinformation propaganda.

4 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To validate the proposed dynamic Mean-Field framework for the analysis of the disinformation propagation, we con-

(a) Magnetization dynamics for different external fields h , with $\mu = 0.5$, $J_{ij} \in [0, 1]$, and $\beta \rightarrow \infty$. The system converges to distinct steady-state magnetization values, influenced by the magnitude and direction of h . Positive h drives alignment toward $m > 0$, negative h leads to $m < 0$, and $h = 0$ maintains near-zero magnetization.

(b) Magnetization dynamics for different external fields h , with $\mu = 0.5$, $J_{ij} \geq 0$, and $\beta \rightarrow \infty$. The system converges to steady-state magnetization values, with positive h driving m to $+1$, negative h driving m to -1 , and $h = 0$ showing slower convergence to an intermediate value, reflecting the balance between interactions and external influence.

Fig. 1: Magnetization dynamics (m) under varying external fields (h) for $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, $\mu = 0.5$. The figure illustrates how stronger external fields ($h = 1.0$) drive faster convergence to higher alignment, while opposing fields ($h = -1.0$) lead to reversed alignment. This highlights the critical role of external influences in shaping collective belief dynamics, with opposing or neutral fields ($h = 0.0$) leading to slower convergence and more fragmented alignment states.

ducted large-scale simulations aiming at analyzing the impact of how memory effects, external pressures and network heterogeneity influence on collective belief dynamics. The simulations targeted the recreation of a wide spectrum of disinformation campaigns, ranging from relatively subtle influence campaigns to highly aggressive ones, through systematic variation of parameters such as coupling strengths, external field intensities and degree of randomness. We finally assessed the framework’s capability to capture phase transitions, providing insights into the disinformation campaign impacts and countermeasures.

In most of the simulations, we include the limit $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ in order to understand the deterministic dynamics in belief alignment, analogous to zero-temperature systems in statistical mechanics. In this regime, β eliminates stochastic noise by making users completely deterministic in aligning their states with the effective field, mirroring the behavior of spin systems in statistical mechanics, where $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ corresponds to a system minimizing its energy under external and internal interactions. In our case, $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ allows us to isolate the fundamental contributions of social interactions, external disinformation campaigns and memory effects to the system’s steady-state behavior and phase transitions, free from the influence of randomness.

Moreover, examining the limit $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ enables the identification of critical thresholds, analogous to phase transitions in physical systems, where the system shifts from disorder (e.g., polarized beliefs) to order (e.g., collective acceptance or rejection of disinformation). This limit can also be considered as a baseline to compare with finite β scenarios, where randomness introduces fluctuations in belief dynamics.

4.1 Dataset Limitations in Modeling Disinformation Spread

The empirical validation of the proposed Mean-Field framework requires datasets that can accurately capture the structural, temporal and behavioural aspects of disinformation spread in social media networks. An ideal dataset would first include different user categories within the network, indicating support, scepticism or neutrality. This specific prerequisite is extremely important in order to analyze the evolution of beliefs over time, providing valuable insights into the dynamics of opinion shifts, the impact of external influences and the effectiveness of counter-disinformation interventions. In addition, an ideal dataset should also include all kind of users’ interactions, such as reposts, replies, mentions, etc., in order to encapsulate the full spectrum of information diffusion dynamics and track engagement patterns especially in case of bots and echo chambers. The incorporation of user interactions can also assist in differentiating between organic discussions and manipulated narratives. Above all, the ideal dataset would include multiple temporal snapshots of the network, in order to analyze the evolution of narratives over time. Unfortunately, existing datasets related to news credibility [45], [46], rumor classification [47], fake news in health [48], including COVID-19 [49], Russia-Ukraine war and refugees [50] among others, often fall short in one or more of these aspects. In particular, most of them either lack detailed user interaction graphs or do not offer time-evolving instances of the network, limiting their applicability for studying disinformation dynamics in a realistic setting.

This gap in data availability poses a significant challenge for validating our framework which requires a rich graph-based representation of user behavior over time. Moreover, existing real-world datasets often face several limitations, in terms of incomplete information, biased data collection, in-

(a) Magnetization dynamics for $h = 0.5$, $J_{ij} \geq 0$, $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, and different memory coefficients (μ). The system converges to $m \approx 1$, with higher memory values ($\mu = 1.2$) causing delayed alignment compared to lower memory values ($\mu = 0.0, 0.5$). The convergence speed decreases as μ increases due to stronger reliance on past states.

(b) Magnetization dynamics for $h = 0.5$, $J_{ij} \in [-0.5, 0.5]$, $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, and different memory coefficients (μ). The system converges to distinct magnetization levels depending on μ , with higher memory values ($\mu = 1.2$) showing slower convergence and lower steady-state magnetization compared to lower memory values μ .

Fig. 2: Magnetization dynamics (m) under varying memory coefficients (μ) and coupling strengths (J_{ij}) for $\beta \rightarrow \infty$. Higher memory coefficients delay the system’s convergence and significantly influence the steady-state alignment, highlighting the role of past beliefs in shaping current dynamics. The impact of coupling strength heterogeneity, particularly the inclusion of negative J_{ij} , introduces distinct equilibrium states, underscoring the complexity of belief dynamics in heterogeneous networks.

sufficient network connectivity details, or restricted generalizability across different social networks and disinformation scenarios. In order to overcome these inherent limitations that come with real-world datasets, we adopt a random graph approach which allow us to demonstrates the flexibility and scalability of our framework, based on a diverse range of network topologies, such as Erdős–Rényi [51], Scale-Free [52] and Small-World [53] structures, which are widely observed in social networks [54]. Additionally, random graphs allow for controlled experiments by systematically varying key parameters such as coupling strengths J_{ij} , memory effects μ and external fields h . This way, we ensure that the results are not tied to specific data constraints, providing a more generalized understanding of belief dynamics and critical thresholds in disinformation spread. The random graph setup also enables us to highlight the robustness of the Mean-Field method, making it adaptable to diverse real-world scenarios.

4.2 Magnetization Dynamics and Belief Alignment in Disinformation Spread

Figure 2 illustrates the magnetization dynamics for a fixed external field $h = 0.5$, a deterministic belief update process $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, and different memory coefficients (μ). More specifically, Figure 2a examines the case where there are only positive coupling strengths J_{ij} . The results indicate that as memory effects increase, the system takes longer to reach its equilibrium magnetization, highlighting the critical role of memory in belief evolution under disinformation influence. Higher memory coefficients introduce inertia in the system, causing users to resist rapid belief shifts despite the presence of strong social and external influences. This effect mirrors real-world disinformation dynamics, where users with strong prior convictions are less susceptible to im-

mediate persuasion, requiring prolonged exposure on disinformation campaigns before changing their perspective. The findings suggest that memory effects can act as a stabilizing factor against abrupt disinformation-driven belief changes, but they may also prolong the persistence of disinformation in the network. In parallel, Figure 2b presents the magnetization dynamics over time for different memory coefficients for heterogeneous coupling strengths $J_{ij} \in [-0.5, +0.5]$ in a social network. These results also highlight the complex role of memory in disinformation spread. While moderate memory effects ($\mu = 0.5$) reinforce belief stability, strong memory retention ($\mu = 1.2$) acts as a stabilizing force that slows adaptation to new information. These findings are completely aligned with real-world disinformation dynamics, where users with strong prior convictions are less likely to be swayed by new narratives [55], even in the presence of persuasive social interactions. The results suggest that when both reinforcing and contradicting influences exist in a network, individuals with high memory effects may sustain polarized belief states, reducing the overall impact of disinformation campaigns.

The magnetization dynamics under varying external fields h , are presented in Figure 1. In particular, Figure 1a depicts the magnetization dynamics different external field values in a social network with heterogeneous coupling strengths $J_{ij} \in [-0.5, +0.5]$, fixed memory coefficient μ and deterministic belief updates. The results indicate that when $h = +1$, the system rapidly aligns with the external influence, reaching a high positive magnetization. Conversely, when $h = -1$, the system quickly converges to a strongly negative magnetization, meaning that the majority of users reject the disinformation. In the absence of an external influence, i.e., $h = 0$, the system remains around $m \approx 0$, indicating a balanced or polarized belief state with no

(a) Phase diagram of magnetization, m , as a function of external field, h , and memory coefficient, μ . The diagram highlights how individuals' memory and susceptibility to disinformation campaigns influence the overall acceptance or rejection of false narratives within a social network.

(b) Heatmap of magnetization, m , as a function of external field, h , and inverse temperature, β . The heatmap illustrates the impact of disinformation campaigns on the collective belief dynamics, identifying critical thresholds for narrative adoption or rejection.

Fig. 3: Heatmaps of magnetization (m) as a function of external field (h) and memory coefficient (μ) under different coupling strengths. These heatmaps illustrate how stronger external fields and higher memory coefficients lead to increased alignment in belief dynamics. When negative coupling strengths (J_{ij}) are introduced, the system exhibits more fragmented and polarized states.

dominant alignment. As it can be readily seen, the role of the external information campaigns in shaping collective beliefs is of paramount importance. A sufficiently strong external influence can drive near-complete belief alignment in either direction, overriding the effects of user interactions. Meanwhile, the case of $h = 0$ suggests that without an external driving force, the network remains divided, most probably due to competing influences within the social structure. This is consistent with real-world observations where coordinated disinformation campaigns can significantly shape public opinion [56], whereas the absence of such influence often leads to neutral opinion distributions [12].

In case the coupling strengths remain positive, i.e., network users reinforce each other's beliefs rather than counteracting opposing views, the system exhibits strong collective alignment, as shown in Figure 1b. The results indicate that when an external influence is present, either $h = +1$ or $h = -1$ the system quickly converges to a highly aligned state, $m \approx 1$ or $m \approx -1$ respectively, demonstrating that positive social reinforcement amplifies the effects of external information campaigns. Even in the absence of an external field the network still evolves toward a relatively high magnetization, showing that belief propagation is primarily driven by internal reinforcement rather than external pressure. The convergence behavior suggests that once a belief becomes prevalent in such a reinforcing structure, reversing or diversifying opinions becomes difficult due to the self-reinforcing nature of social interactions. This reflects real-world patterns in which echo chambers contribute to the amplification of disinformation, creating significant obstacles for fact-checking and counter-messaging efforts [57].

4.3 Critical Thresholds and Phase Transitions in Disinformation Spread

The core results of this paper are presented in Figure 3. More specifically, Figure 3a illustrates the phase diagram of magnetization m as a function of the external field h and the memory coefficient μ . The color gradient represents the steady-state magnetization, where red regions indicate strong belief alignment with disinformation ($m > 0$), blue regions signify rejection of disinformation ($m < 0$) and the transition region near $m \approx 0$ corresponds to a polarized or disordered state. The diagram reveals a clear phase transition: for weak external influence ($h \approx 0$), the system remains near a neutral belief state unless memory effects are low, allowing social interactions to dominate. As h increases, the system exhibits a critical threshold beyond which the majority of nodes adopt the disinformation, with stronger effects at lower μ . At high memory values ($\mu \rightarrow 1$), past states strongly influence current beliefs, making the system more resistant to external disinformation campaigns. This is reflected in the persistence of negative magnetization (blue region) for moderate h , where individuals continue rejecting disinformation despite increasing external pressure. Similarly, for lower memory effects ($\mu \approx 0$), individuals update their beliefs more readily, allowing external fields to rapidly drive the system into full belief alignment, i.e., $m \rightarrow 1$. This highlights the stabilizing role of memory in mitigating rapid disinformation adoption, while also demonstrating that strong external campaigns can still overcome this resistance if h surpasses a critical threshold. As expected, these results align with real-world observations where users with strong prior convictions resist new narratives, while those with weaker memory effects are more susceptible to

influence campaigns [58].

In addition, Figure 3b presents a heatmap of magnetization m as a function of the external field h and the inverse temperature β . The color gradient represents the steady-state belief alignment, where red regions correspond to strong agreement with disinformation ($m > 0$), blue regions indicate rejection of disinformation ($m < 0$) and the white transition zone reflects a polarized or disordered state. As expected, when the external field is strongly positive or negative, the system reaches a high-magnetization state where individuals align with the prevailing influence. However, for weak external influence ($h \approx 0$), the system exhibits a transition region where belief alignment is not well-defined. The effect of inverse temperature (β) is particularly notable: at low values, i.e., $\beta \approx 0$, the system remains disordered regardless of the external field, as randomness dominates decision-making. As β increases, meaning that belief updates become more deterministic, the system transitions into a state where alignment with the external field becomes more pronounced. This highlights how reducing randomness in decision processes (e.g., through stronger conviction or reduced uncertainty) makes users more susceptible to external influence, driving the network users toward collective belief alignment.

4.4 The Role of Uncertainty and Network Topology in Disinformation Propagation

Figure 4a depicts the magnetization dynamics m over time under varying values of the inverse temperature β , with heterogeneous coupling strengths ($J_{ij} \in [-1, 1]$), an external field of $h = 0.5$ and a memory coefficient of $\mu = 0.5$. Each curve represents a different level of randomness in belief updates, ranging from high stochasticity ($\beta = 0.1$) to a fully deterministic regime ($\beta \rightarrow \infty$). The results indicate that at low β , the system exhibits high fluctuations and fails to reach a stable belief alignment due to significant randomness in individual updates. As β increases, belief updates become more deterministic, leading to more stable and higher values of m . In the case of $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, the system converges rapidly to a stable magnetization, demonstrating strong belief alignment with the external field. These observations align with the role of information uncertainty in the disinformation spread. At low β , randomness in user belief updates prevents full convergence, making the system more resilient to external influence but also leading to persistent fluctuations. As β increases, external pressures become more effective in shaping collective beliefs, and the population aligns more strongly with the external field. This result highlights a key vulnerability in real-world disinformation dynamics: **users with reduced uncertainty (higher β) are more likely to adopt the dominant narrative, while those with higher uncertainty (lower β) maintain a more diverse belief distribution.** In other words, people who are more confident in their decisions tend to follow the most popular opinion or the strongest influence around them. On the other hand, those who keep questioning facts are less likely to conform and instead they keep a mix of different opinions. This key result can be incorporated into the design of interventions in order to mitigate the influence of disinformation campaigns by leveraging uncertainty in the belief formation processes.

The impact of network topology on the magnetization dynamics (m) over time is illustrated in Figure 4b. Three distinct, widely-used network structures are compared, namely the Erdős–Rényi, Scale-Free and Small-World networks, revealing the important aspect of network connectivity in shaping belief alignment. The Scale-Free network which is characterized by the presence of high-degree hub nodes, exhibits the highest magnetization, suggesting that influential users facilitate faster and stronger belief adoption within the network. The Erdős–Rényi network follows closely behind, displaying slightly lower but stable magnetization levels, indicating moderate susceptibility to disinformation. In contrast, the Small-World network consistently demonstrates the lowest magnetization, which suggests that the presence of highly clustered local communities acts as a buffer against widespread belief alignment, reducing the overall influence of external fields. These structural properties can be used as a mitigation tactic in disinformation propagation. **Networks with hub nodes, such as Scale-Free structures, are highly susceptible to belief alignment**, as information disseminated through central influencers reaches the entire network fast. In contrast, **networks with strong local clustering, such as Small-World models, demonstrate greater resilience, since localized communities create barriers that slow down the spread of disinformation.**

4.5 Parameter-Driven Intervention Strategies for Mitigation of Disinformation Spread

Fine-tuning the parameters of the proposed Mean-Field framework provides valuable insights for the design of targeted interventions that can be used to mitigate the disinformation spread within various social networks. According to the finding presented above, one of the most effective strategies entails the adjustment of the external field h , which represents the influence of disinformation campaigns or fact-checking efforts. The increase of the the strength of counter-narratives, through the dissemination of verified fact-checking content or public awareness campaigns, results in a shift of the effective field reducing the spread of disinformation. This strategy can reduce the amplification of misleading information disseminated in the social networks. Conversely, if disinformation campaigns remain dominant in shaping the external field, the network rapidly converges to a homogenous belief state, making interventions less effective over time.

Another important factor in the application of effective intervention strategies is the modification of the memory effects (μ), which describe the degree to which past beliefs affect current decision-making. Higher values of μ create cognitive inertia, making users less likely to revise their beliefs, even with new information. Media literacy programs that encourage users to develop skepticism toward unverified claims, is an excellent example since they increase μ , and result in deliberate belief revision while simultaneously reduce susceptibility to fake news. Similarly, modifying the coupling strength J_{ij} can influence the formation of echo chambers in online networks. The introduction of diverse viewpoints into the already deployed recommendation algorithms [59] used by the social network operators or the design of specific policies that increase exposure to opposing

(a) Effect of information uncertainty, β , on belief alignment, m , in a simulated social network. The figure shows how the system's response to external disinformation campaign (h) evolves as uncertainty decreases (increases). With $\mu = 0.5$ accounting for memory effects, the results highlight the critical role of reduced randomness in enhancing susceptibility to disinformation campaigns. The network incorporates heterogeneous interaction strengths, $J_{ij} \in [-1, 1]$, to reflect real-world social structures.

(b) Impact of network topology on belief alignment, m , under disinformation influence. The plot compares three social network structures, i.e., Erdős-Rényi, Scale-Free and Small-World networks, revealing the structural differences that shape the propagation of disinformation. For a fixed external pressure ($h = 0.5$) and memory effects ($\mu = 0.5$), the results reveal that Scale-Free networks exhibit the highest alignment, indicating their susceptibility to disinformation due to influential hub nodes.

Fig. 4: Analysis of belief alignment (m) in social networks under varying disinformation dynamics. The results highlight the connection between external influences (h), memory effects (μ) and network topology in shaping collective belief dynamics.

perspectives can modify the network structures in such a manner that polarization is minimized, thus inhibiting the dissemination of disinformation.

Network topology is also a key aspect in controlling the speed and scale of the disinformation spread. Rate-limiting content virality, applying stricter content moderation policies or prioritizing less unverified content, all serve to effectively increase the path length in the network, reducing the rate at which disinformation reaches a critical mass. Finally, adjusting the inverse temperature (β), which governs decision randomness, is another effective intervention mechanism. Higher β values lead to deterministic decision-making, where users strongly align are highly conforming to external and social pressures. On the other hand, lower β values, introduce a high degree of uncertainty in decision-making, thus stimulating a range of opinions and minimizing group conformity.

Adjusting the framework's parameters enables the design of optimal intervention strategies that can disrupt disinformation spread, make beliefs more resilient and foster a more diverse and well-informed information ecosystem.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced a novel Mean-Field framework for modeling the spread of disinformation in social networks, based on well-established statistical mechanics principles. The integration of varying, heterogeneous coupling strengths, memory effects and external influences, provides a thorough perspective on the mechanisms through which disinformation propagates within online communities. The three-state Potts model effectively captures the range of opinion states, allowing for a more realistic representation of users who may adopt, reject or remain neutral toward

false narratives. One of the primary contributions of this work is the incorporation of memory effects that considers cognitive inertia and the tendency of individuals to retain prior beliefs even in the presence of external influences. Our findings show that higher memory coefficients significantly reduce belief shifts, reinforcing polarization and undermining counter-disinformation efforts. This observation is in line with real-world scenarios where users with strong prior beliefs resist fact-checking, necessitating long-term engagement strategies to debunk deceptions.

Furthermore, the role of external fields in shaping belief alignment was also examined, demonstrating that sufficiently strong disinformation campaigns can drive an entire population toward homogeneous belief states, while weaker or competing influences result in polarized or fragmented networks [60]. Monte Carlo simulations revealed the critical thresholds at which disinformation becomes self-sustaining, providing insights for policy makers and platform moderators aiming to intervene before widespread adoption. The paper also explored the impact of network topology, highlighting the importance of structural interventions, such as targeted counter-messaging in highly connected nodes, to contain false narratives before they cascade through the network.

Beyond its theoretical contributions, the proposed framework serves as a basis for future extensions, including dynamic network adaptation and the incorporation of agent-based decision models that capture the evolution of trust in online environments. Future research will explore empirical validation with observational social media data, fine-tuning the model parameters to reflect realistic user behaviors and refining intervention strategies to mitigate the societal impact of disinformation and manipulation campaigns.

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